

Historical Significance of the Great Silk Road

Tursunov Jovli Narzullaevich

Associate Professor, Candidate of History, Department of History and Philosophy, Denov Management and Pedagogical Institute

The ancient Great Silk Road has been connecting the East and West for centuries. B.C. From the 2nd century, the connection of trade routes connected China to the Roman Empire. The Silk Road, associated with the name of the Chinese ambassador Zhang Jian, gained widespread development in the I-II centuries. Trade with China was mainly carried out by Central Asian intermediary merchants. In 97, the Chinese traveler Tan In reached the Persian Gulf. In May 100, Titian reached Longzhou, but the difficulties in the journey prevented him from connecting China with Rome.

In the III-VI centuries, the Silk Road was used not only for trade but also for religious purposes, that is, Buddhist monks went from China to India.

In the 6th-10th centuries, the importance of the Silk Road increased, that is, relations between Byzantium and the Arabs with China were established.

In the Silk Road, silk was considered the main product of its fineness, elegance, and beauty. The silk was torn to pieces. The length and width of silk fabrics were determined by law. In the Han period, the width of silk products was 0.5 meters, the length was 9 meters. The first archaeologist of the Silk Road, A. Stein, discovered a piece of silk near Dunhuan and found a hieroglyphic inscription on its corner. The inscription indicated the place, size, weight, and price of the fabric.

In addition to silk, pottery, gold, iron, weapons, rice, wine, mirror, bamboo were imported from China, and from Vietnam - corals, pearls, and precious stones. Gold, silver, iron, lead, woollen cloths, carpets, sugar, tortoiseshell cups and ivory were imported from India, hair and yarn, dishes and weapons, carpets and precious stones from the Persian Gulf and the Near East. From Central Asia, carpets, horses, dry, tame animals from Samarkand, pepper, wine, bottles, paper were traded. The Uyghurs exchanged one horse with the Chinese for 4.5 whole pieces (0.5x9) of silk. By the 7th century, the price of a horse had increased by 10 silk pieces.

It was on the Great Silk Road that the check method was launched. Every 25-30 km along the entire road, caravanserais were built. There were restrooms with 2-3 rooms, as well as separate places for servants, camels, horses and other animals attached to the caravan. There were several types of domestic services in these caravanserais. There were medical workers, blacksmiths, writers, translators, and servants. Sometimes caravans were very large and long. One such caravan was the one sent by the Arab caliph al-Muktadir to the Bulgarian Shah in 922. This caravan consisted of 3,000 camels, horses, and animals, with 5,000 men. Among them were servants, guards, merchants, artists, diplomats, scholars, and travelers.

Marco Polo, who visited China in the 12th-14th centuries, called these roads the "Great Silk Road." In the 15th century, with the advent of sea routes, the importance of the Silk Road decreased.

In the second half of the 19th century, European states began to survey Central Asia. Muhammad ibn Hamid, a young Indian who had traversed the snowy passes of Karakorum, organized a mysterious mission to Asia. The main purpose of the trip is to gather information for the Queen of England. Muhammad ibn Hamid went on a journey in 1860 and fell ill and died during the journey. William Johnson was sent to find out about his death. He found Muhammad Hamid's diary and sent it to Captain T. G.

Montgomery. His notebook is buried in sand, a time when culture flourished. He described a city with several gold mines. This was a re-discovery of the Silk Road by Western scholars.

In 1877, in Berlin, Ferdinand Freiherr von Richthofen published "China. The results of personal journeys and deep research" were published in the publishing house of D. Reiner. F.F. Rechtgofen (1833-1905) was a German geographer and traveler who studied the nature of China. During his travels, he studied the geography, geology, fauna and flora of China, as well as its religious and state system, the spiritual life of its people and its history. After Muhammad ibn Hamid's famous discovery, the great powers began to send their scholars to Turkestan.

In 1895, the Swedish geographer Sven Gedin visited the lost cities of Taklakon. Later along with him was the first archaeologist of the Silk Road, Aurel Steine. A. Stein (1862-1943) was an archaeologist-geographer of Hungarian origin. He conducted research in the Indian subcontinent, Afghanistan, Iran, East China, Iraq, and many other Eastern cities. In 1900, he waited for the snow to melt in Kashmir and then set out for the ancient caravan route. His explorations in Khotan (the southern part of the Silk Road, Turfan, Loulan) made him famous. But a study in Dunhuan (1906-1909) brought him secular popularity. The finds found in Dunhuan were transferred by A. Stein to England in 1907 and transferred to the British Museum. After that, the interest in this road increased even more.

In 1906-1908, the scientific expedition of the French Chinese scholar Paul Pelliot (1878-1945) was organized in Xinjiang. In his scientific works, P. Pelliot writes about Daoism and Buddhism, religions that exist mainly in China. He transferred the manuscript materials found in Xinjiang to the National Library of Paris.

The Great Silk Road, which interested French and English scientists, also interested Russian scientists. The Academy of Sciences organized the first special expedition to East Turkestan to study the Great Silk Road. It was headed by D. A. Clements. In 1900, the Russian Archaeological Society decided to organize a large 3-year expedition to Tarim. But the Ministry of Finance refused to pay these expenses, and the decision of this issue was taken by French, English, Japanese and Chinese scientists.

Four expeditions of German travelers, A. von Le Coke and A. Grünwedel, were organized one after another. Data was actively collected by Japanese Count Sesin Otani and American G. Warney. The Russian comet sent M. M. Berezovsky to Kuch. Caves with Buddha's images, inscriptions, and manuscripts were found in it. M.M. Berezovsky (1848-1912) was a Russian traveler, mathematician, who worked in Kucha in 1905 and until December 1907. During this time, he discovered more than 20 cities. In 1908, an exhibition of his findings was opened in the royal courtyard. Among the findings of M.M. Berezovsky, the manuscripts of the Sanskrit, Uyghur, and Tokhar script are of great interest to world scholars. After that, a new expedition was organized to East Turkestan. It was headed by Academician S. F. Oldenburg and artist, traveler, ethnographer, archaeologist S. M. Dudin (1863-1921). Their scientific discoveries became the centers of Buddhist and Islamic culture in Central Asia. S. F. Oldenburg gave his finds to the Oriental Department of the Asian Museum and the Hermitage. The study of the "Great Silk Road" by European scientists was interrupted by the beginning of the First World War.

The famous scientist Ibrahim Muminov gives information about this period: "The best atlases in the world are produced in Samarkand."

Mahmud Kutlukov's study, based on Chinese, Arabic, Persian, and other sources on the part of the Silk Road that passed through China, showed that as a result of the change of the Ming dynasty (1368-1644), which ruled in China in 1279-1367, and the formation of the Moghulistan state in Turkestan (1348-1516), a sharp change took place in the Turkestan-Chinese relations. The disruption of trade relations between these two regions was caused by the Ming dynasty's initiation of an invasion war to conquer the city of Kumul, which was the main hub of the caravan route, in order to conquer the "Silk Road." Kumul went to China and then to Mongolia. Of course, this war, which lasted more than a hundred years, will exhaust

the merchants. Despite the fact that Kumul fell to China in 1499, the merchants of Western and Eastern Turkestan forced a treaty to return the Khan of Moghulistan to Ahmad Khan and the Chinese officials who fell into his hands. At the same time, the letter of the ruler of Tashkent, Mahmud Khan, to the Chinese Khagan was of great importance, and for a time trade relations were improved.

According to M. Kutlukov, the city of Kumul was liberated in 1513 by Mansurhan, son of Ahmad Khan. However, the struggle for this city continued after the Mongol khans of Yarkand (1465-1759) and Dzungar (1635-1755) against the invasion wars of the Ming and Qing dynasties (1644-1911) until the first half of the 18th century. This situation led to the reduction of China-Central Asia trade relations.

According to Chinese sources, A. Khojaev indicates that the Sino-Jungarian trade agreement was concluded in 1746, according to which Jungarian merchants were allowed to travel to China for trade once every 4 years. This treaty also lost its force in 1756, when the Dzungar Khanate was conquered by the Manchus.

Thus, from the above information, it can be seen that the decrease in the inflow of Chinese goods into Turkestan was caused not by the opening of sea routes, but by the invasion wars of the Ming dynasty khans who came to power in China in the 14th century in relation to the lands of Mongolia. As a result, trade between China and Turkestan decreased, and the flow of Chinese goods westward decreased. However, this did not mean that trade relations in Turkestan were weakening. Of course, the decline in trade between this region and China to some extent affected the trade of Turkestan. Traditional trade, however, continued along ancient caravan routes.

Therefore, trade relations in eastern Turkestan, which was the most remote region of Turkestan, also declined in the 17th century. The Portuguese traveler Benedikt Goes, who arrived in this country in 1603-1605 with a caravan from India, writes that the cities of Yorkent, Kashgar, Aksu, Turfan are major trading centers and are full of merchants from different places. Grigory Nikolaevich Potanin gives the following information about the economic situation of this land before the conquest of the Manchus in the XVIII century based on materials from the Russian archive: "Bukharians (small Bukharans, that is, Kashgari), living in the southern cities, enjoy the fruits of their early education, study poets, engage in gardening, weaving, (particularly), weaving and trade. Their caravans reached the farthest corners of Asia, as in the medieval Republic of Genoa (Italy). "Bukharan merchants can be found in Ashtarkhan, Tobol, Kyahta and Arhangelsk."

List of literature

1. Ражабов Қ.Хасанов Ф. Қандов Б.Ўзбекистон республикасининг мустақиллик солномаси.Т."Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси".2011.-Б.53.
2. Ғуломов С. Убайдуллаева Р. Аҳмедов Э. Мустақил Ўзбекистон.Т."Ислон университети".2003.- Б.114.
3. Турсунов С.Қобилов Э.Муртазоев Б. Пардаев Т. Сурхондарё тарихи.Т."Шарқ".2004.-Б.526.
4. Турсунов С.Қобилов Э.Муртазоев Б. Пардаев Т. Сурхондарё тарихи.Т."Шарқ".2004.-Б.526.
5. Yusupovich, Koshakov Safarali. "Material Culture in Zoroastrian Religion." *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education* (2994-9521) 2.6 (2024): 715-719.
6. Isayev, Oybek. "THE ORGANIZATION OF A ZOO IN THE CITY OF TERMIZ, SOUTHERN REGION OF UZBEKISTAN." *Interpretation and researches* (2024).
7. Isayev, Oybek. "THE CULTURAL LIFE IN SURKHAN OASIS: INFORMING OF ACHIEVEMENTS AND PROBLEMS BASED ON ARCHIVAL MATERIALS (1925–1941 YEARS)." *The Light of Islam* 2019.4 (2019): 31.

8. Qudratov, Namoz, and Oybek Isayev. "DENOV BOZORI FAOLIYATI 1946-1961-YILLAR." Talqin va tadqiqotlar (2024).
9. Oybek, PhD Isaev. "In the Study of the History of Surkhandarya in the 30s of the XX Century, as a Historical Source." Eurasian Journal of History, Geography and Economics 7 (2022): 100-102.
10. Исаев, Ойбек Ахмед. "Освещение проблем образования Сурханского оазиса в архивных материалах (1920-1930 гг.)." Бюллетень науки и практики 6.8 (2020): 289-294.
11. Yusupovich, Koshakov Safarali. "Material Culture in Zoroastrian Religion." Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521) 2.6 (2024): 715-719.
12. Юсупович, Қўшоқов Сафарали. "ЗАРДУШТИЙЛИК ДИНИДА ДАФН МАРОСИМЛАР ТАЛҚИНИ." MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH 3 (2023): 201-208.
13. Yusupovich, Kushakov Safarali. "THE ROLE OF ANCIENT BACTERIA AND MARGIA IN THE ESTABLISHMENT OF ZARDUSTIYA." Chief Editor 12.
14. Бабаева, Ситора Рuzимахматовна. "Взгляд на историю топливно-энергетического комплекса Сурханского оазиса." Бюллетень науки и практики 7.2 (2021): 394-397.
15. Boboeva, Sitora Ruzimahmatovna. "HISTORY OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE FUEL INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN." World Economics and Finance Bulletin 4 (2021): 6-8.
16. Бобоева, С. Р. "Исторические топонимы вдоль торгового пути Термез-«Железные ворота»." Бюллетень науки и практики 6.2 (2020): 347-355.
17. Бобоева, Ситора. "БОЙСУН ТАРИХИЙ ТОПОНИМИ ҲАҚИДА." ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ 21 (2019).
18. Sitora Ruzimakhmatova Boboeva. (2023). THE EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF ELECTRIC NETWORKS IN THE SURKHAN OASIS. (USING THE EXAMPLE OF 1914-1941). Scientific Impulse, 2(13), 300–306.
19. Kultaeva, Fazilat. "Study of ergonyms in uzbeki linguistics." World Bulletin of Social Sciences 16 (2022): 11-14.
20. Kultayeva, Fazilat. "Ergonimlarning jahon va o 'zbek tilshunosligida o 'rganilishi." E Conference Zone. 2022.
21. KULTAEVA, Fazilat. "Analysis of ergonomic units at the onomastic level." (2022).
22. Bakhtiyorovna, Kultayeva Fazilat. "Production Characteristics of Ergonomics." American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769) 1.10 (2023): 666-670.
23. Fazilat, Kultayeva. "ERGONIMLARNI MA'NOVIY VA VAZIFAVIY KLASSIFIKATSIYALASH XUSUSIDA." «CONTEMPORARY TECHNOLOGIES OF COMPUTATIONAL LINGUISTICS» 2.22.04 (2024): 556-560.
24. Fazilat, Kultayeva. "FANDA ERGONIMLARNING O 'RGANILISHI XUSUSIDA." Philological research: language, literature, education 2.2 (2024).
25. Yusupovich, Koshakov Safarali. "Material Culture in Zoroastrian Religion." Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521) 2.6 (2024): 715-719.
26. Юсупович, Қўшоқов Сафарали. "ЗАРДУШТИЙЛИК ДИНИДА ДАФН МАРОСИМЛАР ТАЛҚИНИ." MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH 3 (2023): 201-208.

27. Yusupovich, Kushakov Safarali. "THE ROLE OF ANCIENT BACTERIA AND MARGIA IN THE ESTABLISHMENT OF ZARDUSTIYA." Chief Editor 12.
28. Юсупович, Қўшоқов Сафарали. "ЗАРДУШТИЙЛИК ДИНИ ТАЛҚИНИ ВА УНИНГ МОДДИЙ МАДАНИЯТДА АКС ЭТИШИ." Scientific Impulse 1.12 (2023): 246-251.
29. Kushokov, Safarali. "EARLY RELIGIOUS SIGNS OF THE TERRITORIES OF UZBEKISTAN." Research and Implementation 1.3 (2023): 71-77.
30. Yusupovich, Kushokov Safarali. "FACTORS WHICH ARE THE BASIS OF THE FIRST RELIGIOUS VIEWS." Scientific Impulse 1.11 (2023): 140-145.
31. Юсупович, Қўшоқов Сафарали. "ЗАРДУШТИЙЛИК ДИНИ ТАЛҚИНИ ВА УНИНГ МОДДИЙ МАДАНИЯТДА АКС ЭТИШИ." Scientific Impulse 1.12 (2023): 246-251.
32. Yusupovich, Kushakov Safarali. "Orta Osiyoda ilk diniy qarashlarning oziga xosligi." Scientific Impulse 1.11 (2023): 115-120.
33. Юсупович, Қўшоқов Сафарали. "ЗАРДУШТИЙЛИК ДИНИ ТАЛҚИНИ ВА УНИНГ МОДДИЙ МАДАНИЯТДА АКС ЭТИШИ." Scientific Impulse 1.12 (2023): 246-251.